

ASSESSMENT OF CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACTS ON VULNERABLE POPULATIONS IN BENUE STATE, NORTH-CENTRAL NIGERIA

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Abstract: Benue State, Nigeria, faces severe environmental and climate challenges affecting natural resources, livelihoods, and human security. Vulnerable groups, particularly women and youth, are disproportionately impacted, yet their experiences remain under-documented. This study examines community-perceived climate change impacts and identifies adaptation and mitigation opportunities. Using a mixed-method approach, data were collected from 400 households and 91 key informants. Findings show 52.5% of households that participated in the study rely on crop farming, with firewood (49.7%) and charcoal (27.1%) as primary energy sources. Climate awareness is low, especially among women (67.3% unaware). Respondents reported increased temperatures (67.5%), reduced rainfall (53.3%), and hazards like flooding and heatwaves. Key challenges include rising pest and crop diseases and declining yields. Notably, men are more likely than women to adopt adaptive strategies, largely due to disparities in resource access. The study highlights the socio-economic, environmental, and gender dimensions of climate change, stressing the need for inclusive, multi-sectoral interventions to enhance resilience.

Keywords: Climate Change, Natural Resources, Agriculture, Livelihood, Adaptation, Vulnerability, Gender

Introduction

Climate change remains one of the most pressing global challenges of the 21st century. However, its impacts are not evenly distributed, with Africa standing out as particularly vulnerable due to its limited adaptive capacity, overdependence on climate-sensitive sectors, particularly agriculture and chronic underinvestment in financial and technical resources (Mbah and Ezegwu, 2024, 2025). The continent is already experiencing pronounced climate-related challenges such as rising temperatures, unpredictable rainfall patterns, and an increase in the frequency and severity of extreme weather events, including droughts, floods, and storms (IPCC, 2023; Trisos et

al., 2022; Ezegwu and Mbah, 2025). Africa has already warmed by approximately 1.3°C above pre-industrial levels, surpassing the global average of 1.1°C. Forecasts suggest that the continent could experience a further rise in temperature beyond 1.5°C by the middle of this century. These trends pose grave threats to food security, human health, livelihoods, and economic development across the region (Sylla et al., 2018; Thomas and Nigam, 2018; Onyeaka et al., 2024; Raheem et al., 2025; Saleem et al., 2024).

Despite the urgency of responding to climate change, African countries face considerable barriers to adaptation. These include a lack of financial investment, weak institutional frameworks, limited access to technological innovations, and inadequate environmental data for planning and early warning systems (Thomas et al., 2021; Achakpa et al., 2023). Furthermore, significant knowledge gaps persist regarding the ways in which different groups, especially marginalised and vulnerable populations, are uniquely affected by climate change. Understanding how social, economic, and cultural factors, including gender roles, age, and disability, shape vulnerability and resilience remains insufficiently developed (Thompson-Hall et al., 2016; Oluwatimilehin & Ayanlade, 2021). Such insights are essential for formulating effective adaptation and mitigation strategies that are inclusive and equitable.

This study seeks to contribute to the growing body of knowledge by evaluating the impacts of climate change on vulnerable populations in Benue State, located in Nigeria's North-Central geopolitical zone. Often referred to as the "food basket of the nation," Benue State plays a pivotal role in Nigeria's agricultural sector (Ahungwa et al., 2013; Udoinyang, 2025). It is a major producer of staple crops such as yams, maize, rice, cassava, beans, and sorghum (Adadu, 2024). The state's economy is heavily reliant on rain-fed agriculture, making it particularly susceptible to climate variability and extremes. However, in recent years, Benue has experienced increasing environmental challenges that have threatened both livelihoods and food security. These include recurring climate-induced conflicts between farmers and pastoralists (Abugu et al., 2015; Madu et al., 2021), destructive flood events (Ade, 2021; Adadu et al., 2024), worsening water and sanitation crises (Utsev et al., 2012; Aondoakaa et al., 2012; Egwuaba and Sunday, 2025), and progressive land degradation and soil infertility (Ali et al., 2021; Igomu et al., 2023).

While the impacts of climate change are felt across all segments of society, they are disproportionately borne by vulnerable groups such as women, children, the elderly, persons with disabilities, and marginalised communities. These populations are more likely to suffer the adverse consequences of climate-related disruptions due to underlying socio-economic inequalities, cultural norms, and institutional limitations. In Benue State, for instance, female-headed farming households tend to be more vulnerable to climate variability and extreme events compared to male-headed households. This is largely due to structural barriers such as limited access to productive land, agricultural inputs, credit facilities, and extension services factors that constrain their ability to adapt and recover from climate shocks (Onah et al., 2023).

Moreover, existing research highlights that climate change intensifies existing disparities in access to food, water, and health services. For example, extreme weather events such as floods and prolonged droughts have been shown to disproportionately affect women and children, not only by disrupting agricultural productivity but also by

increasing the burden of care and domestic labour, especially in water-scarce environments (Obiora, 2014; Ibaishwa & Abaagu, 2018; International Alert, 2024). In situations where access to clean water is compromised, women and girls often walk longer distances to fetch water, increasing exposure to health risks and limiting opportunities for education or economic engagement. Additionally, internally displaced persons (IDPs), many of whom have been uprooted due to climate-induced conflicts or natural disasters, face heightened exposure to disease, food insecurity, and social exclusion (Inyang and Effiong, 2022; Egwuaba and Sunday, 2025).

Given the centrality of agriculture to livelihoods in Benue State, there is a critical need to understand the specific ways in which climate change impacts vulnerable groups and to assess the adaptive measures available to them. This understanding will help inform more targeted and responsive policies. For example, improving access to climate information services, investing in climate-resilient agricultural practices, and integrating gender-sensitive and inclusive approaches into policy frameworks are essential to safeguarding the wellbeing of affected communities.

This study argues that addressing climate vulnerabilities requires a multidimensional approach one that goes beyond environmental responses to include social protection, equity in resource access, and the strengthening of local governance and community-based resilience strategies. By generating empirical evidence from Benue State, this research aims to inform state and national policymakers on the design of equitable adaptation strategies that leave no one behind. The findings can also support Nigeria's broader commitments to global frameworks such as the Paris Agreement, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction. While climate change presents a universal threat, its impacts in regions such as Benue State are magnified by existing socio-economic vulnerabilities. Understanding the differentiated impacts of climate change and tailoring adaptation strategies to address the specific needs of marginalised groups is crucial for achieving resilient, inclusive, and sustainable development. This study contributes towards that objective by placing vulnerable populations at the centre of climate discourse and action.

2.0 Literature

a. Temperature and Rainfall

Temperature and rainfall are critical climatic variables that significantly influence ecological systems, agricultural productivity, and human livelihoods. Temperature refers to the degree of heat in the atmosphere, and its rise intensifies evaporation, alters growing seasons, and increases the frequency of heatwaves (IPCC, 2023). Rainfall, or precipitation, denotes the amount of water falling to the Earth's surface, typically measured in millimetres. Irregular rainfall patterns such as delayed onset, early cessation, or reduced intensity disrupt water availability, crop cycles, and soil moisture, particularly in rain-fed agricultural systems (UNDP, 2022). In Sub-Saharan Africa, rising temperatures and erratic rainfall have contributed to increased droughts and floods, impacting food security and increasing vulnerability among rural populations (UNEP, 2021; Trisos et al., 2022). Understanding these changes is essential for developing climate-resilient strategies, especially in regions like Benue State, Nigeria, where agriculture is highly climate-dependent.

b. Climate Vulnerability

Climate vulnerability refers to the degree to which individuals, communities, or systems are exposed, sensitive, and unable to cope with the adverse impacts of climate change (Bedeke, 2023). It is a multidimensional concept encompassing three interrelated elements: exposure to climate hazards (e.g., floods, droughts), **sensitivity** to those hazards (e.g., reliance on agriculture), and adaptive capacity the ability to respond and recover from climatic

shocks (IPCC, 2023). In sub-Saharan Africa, limited infrastructure, poverty, and governance gaps heighten vulnerability, particularly among marginalised populations such as women, children, and the elderly (Trisos et al., 2022; Thomas et al., 2021). In Nigeria, climate vulnerability is intensified by environmental degradation, weak institutional support, and socio-economic inequalities, particularly in agrarian states like Benue (Oluwatimilehin and Ayanlade, 2021). Understanding climate vulnerability is crucial for designing context-specific and equitable adaptation strategies that reduce risk and enhance resilience in highly exposed regions.

c. Household Access to Energy and Sources of Water

Household access to energy and sources of water refers to the availability, reliability, affordability, and sustainability of essential resources for domestic consumption, including cooking, lighting, and drinking. In many low- and middle-income regions, particularly in rural areas of sub-Saharan Africa, households rely on traditional biomass (firewood, charcoal) and unimproved water sources such as rivers and shallow wells, which expose users to health and environmental risks (World Bank, 2022). Limited access to clean energy and potable water negatively affects health, productivity, education, and gender equity, as women and children often bear the burden of resource collection (UNICEF, 2023). Improving access requires integrated infrastructure, policy reforms, and decentralised service delivery mechanisms that promote renewable energy and safe water supply (IRENA, 2021; WHO/UNICEF, 2020). This concept is crucial for assessing vulnerability and resilience in climate-affected households.

d. Climatic Phenomena and Vulnerable Groups

Climatic phenomena such as rising temperatures, erratic rainfall, floods, and droughts are becoming increasingly frequent and intense due to global climate change. These phenomena disproportionately affect vulnerable groups, including women, children, the elderly, persons with disabilities, and marginalised communities, whose adaptive capacity is often constrained by socio-economic and institutional inequalities (IPCC, 2023; International Alert, 2024). In regions like Benue State, Nigeria, where livelihoods are heavily dependent on rain-fed agriculture, such climatic shifts heighten food insecurity, water scarcity, and displacement risks (Oluwatimilehin & Ayanlade, 2021). Vulnerability is not solely environmental but deeply shaped by social structures, including access to land, education, credit, and participation in decision-making processes (Onah et al., 2023). Recognising the intersection between climatic stressors and social vulnerability is crucial for designing inclusive and equitable adaptation strategies that protect at-risk populations and enhance resilience to ongoing and future climate impacts.

3.0 Materials and Methods

3.1 The Study Area

Benue State, commonly referred to as the "food basket of Nigeria," is located in the north-central region of Nigeria and comprises 23 local government areas (LGAs) across three administrative zones: Benue North-East (Zone A), Benue North-West (Zone B), and Benue South (Zone C). Geographically, the state is located on longitude 7° 47' and 10° 0' East; Latitude 6° 25' and 8° 8' North; and lies within the lower Benue River trough, sharing boundaries with several Nigerian states and a short border with Cameroon. With a population of approximately 4.25 million (NBS, 2023), Benue State is characterised by a tropical AW climate, experiencing distinct wet (April–October) and dry (November–March) seasons, with annual rainfall ranging from 2000–2500 mm and temperatures fluctuating between 21–37°C (Tyubee, 2005). The state features low-lying, undulating terrain with notable hilly areas near the Cameroon border. River Benue and its tributary, River Katsina-Ala, are dominant geographical

features. As part of the Guinea savanna belt, the region supports diverse vegetation and is predominantly agrarian, with key crops including rice, yam, cassava, maize, and sorghum.

3.2 Methods

This study adopted a mixed-methods approach, incorporating household surveys, key informant interviews (KIIs), and focus group discussions (FGDs). The study population included households, government agencies, civil society organisations, private sector actors, academia, and community leaders.

A multi-stage sampling technique was employed, stratifying Benue State into its three senatorial zones. Two local government areas (LGAs) were randomly selected from each zone. Within each selected LGA, two communities were randomly chosen, and every fourth household was systematically sampled. Using the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) 2023 projected population of 4.5 million, the average household size was calculated based on Benue State’s average household size of 5.63 (NBS, 2023). The sample size of 400 households was determined using Taro Yamane’s formula (Taro Yamane, 1973; Uakarn et al., 2021) and proportionally distributed across the selected LGAs. Additionally, 24 FGDs were conducted with youth, women, men, internally displaced persons (IDPs), and persons with disabilities (PWDs). Sixty-five KIIs were held with traditional leaders, religious leaders, civil society representatives, government officials, and academics.

Thirty trained enumerators collected data over seven days using structured questionnaires via KoboCollect and conducted face-to-face interviews. The questionnaire was pilot-tested and validated by an academic expert in the field. Descriptive statistics were applied for quantitative analysis using SPSS and Excel, while qualitative data were transcribed, coded, and thematically analysed using an inductive approach. Both the quantitative and qualitative data were triangulated and synthesised into structured reports. Approval for the study was obtained from the Benue State Ministry of Water Resources and Environment. Informed consent was secured from all participants before data collection.

4.0 Results

4.1 Socio-economic Characteristics of Households

The socio-economic characteristics of the households, including sex, educational level, sources of income, and economic activities, were identified. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Socio-economic Characteristics of Households

What is your level of education?	Female		Male		Grand %
	Freq	%	Freq	%	
Non-formal	38	18.91%	16	8.04%	13.50%
Primary school	29	14.43%	17	8.54%	11.50%
Secondary school	84	41.79%	80	40.20%	41.00%
Tertiary education	45	22.39%	72	36.18%	29.25%
Vocational School	5	2.49%	14	7.04%	4.75%
Are crops farming your only source of income?					
No	101	50.25%	89	44.72%	47.50%
Yes	100	49.75%	110	55.28%	52.50%
Which other economic activities do you engage in?					
Animal rearing	9	8.91%	8	8.99%	8.95%

Casual work	5	4.95%	13	14.61%	9.47%
Entrepreneur	30	29.70%	23	25.84%	27.89%
Others		0.00%	4	4.49%	2.11%
Salaried work	11	10.89%	27	30.34%	20.00%
Trading	46	45.54%	14	15.73%	31.58%
Estimated monthly income					
101,000-170,00	19	9.45%	27	13.57%	11.50%
171,000-240,000	19	9.45%	13	6.53%	8.00%
31,000-100,000	66	32.84%	64	32.16%	32.50%
Above 240,000	4	1.99%	8	4.02%	3.00%
Below 30,000	93	46.27%	87	43.72%	45.00%
Grand Total	201		199		100%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The results presented in Table 1 reveal that the sample population consisted of 201 females (50.3%) and 199 males (49.8%). In terms of educational attainment, the majority of females 84(41.7%) and males 80(40.2%) had attained secondary education. However, more males 72 (36.18%) than females 45 (22.39%) had tertiary education. This suggests that males had greater opportunities to acquire higher education compared to females. Furthermore, income data indicate that only 4 females (1.99%) and 8 males (4.02%) earned above 240,000 naira per month. The majority 93 females (46.27%) and 87 males (43.72%) earned below 30,000 naira (approximately 20 US dollars) per month. This indicates that most individuals, regardless of gender, earned below the previous Nigerian minimum wage of 30,000 naira per month. This wage level is significantly below the World Bank’s international poverty line of \$2.15 per person per day, suggesting that most households in the study communities live in extreme poverty. As a result, they likely struggle to meet basic needs and are more vulnerable to the impacts of climate change.

Additionally, 210 respondents (52.5%) relied on crop farming as their primary source of income, while 190 respondents (47.5%) had alternative sources of income. Among those with other income sources, the majority of females 46 (45.54%) were engaged in trading compared to 14 males (15.73%). In contrast, the majority of males 27 (30.34%) were salaried workers compared to 11 females (10.89%). The high dependency on crop farming highlights the community’s direct vulnerability to climate change impacts on agriculture.

4.2 Household Access to Energy and Sources of Water

The sources of fuel and water supply that households and communities rely on often influence their resilience to climate change. The results on sources of fuel and water supply are disaggregated by the study LGAs to understand the spatial nature of access to these resources. The findings are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Households Sources of Fuel and Water Supply

LGA		Agatu	Buruku	Kwande	Logo	Makurdi	Oju	Total	Total %
Variable	Categories	%	%	%	%	%	%		
Sources of fuel	Firewood	57.4	59.62	48.65	96.55	33.88	34.93	317	49.70%
	Gas/LPG	8.2	3.85	11.49	0.00	21.49	6.16	61	9.60%

used for cooking	Charcoal	29.5	26.92	23.65	0.00	40.50	29.45	173	27.10%
	Biogas	0.0	0.00	2.70	1.72	0.00	0.00	5	0.80%
	Kerosene	4.9	4.81	10.81	0.00	2.48	3.42	32	5.00%
	Electricity	0.0	1.92	2.03	0.00	1.65	1.37	9	1.40%
	Briquette/rice husk	0.0	2.88	0.00	0.00	0.00	24.66	39	6.10%
	Others, specify	0.0	0.00	0.68	1.72	0.00	0.00	2	0.30%
	Total		100.0	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	638
Sources of drinking water	Piped/borehole	1.1	36.05	9.40	41.77	56.56	37.06	232	30.70%
	Well	36.7	30.81	47.65	31.65	18.85	4.90	212	28.10%
	River/stream	26.7	2.91	19.46	12.66	2.46	23.78	105	13.90%
	Rainwater	33.3	29.65	21.48	12.66	4.92	27.97	169	22.40%
	Spring	0.0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.10	3	0.40%
	water vendor	2.2	0.00	2.01	1.27	17.21	4.20	33	4.40%
	Others	0.0	0.58	0	0	0	0	1	0.10%
Total		100	100	100	100	100	100	755	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024. Multiple Response

The results presented in Table 2 indicate that the majority of households in the study communities, specifically 317 (49.7%), rely on firewood as their primary source of fuel. This is followed by 173 households (27.1%) using charcoal, 61 households (9.6%) relying on gas/LP, and only 0.8% utilising biogas. These findings suggest that fuel sources among the LGAs are relatively similar.

The results presented in Table 2 indicate that a majority of households in Agatu (36.7%) and Kwande (47.7%) primarily depend on shallow or deep wells for their drinking water. In contrast, 36.1% of households in Buruku, 41.8% in Logo, 56.7% in Makurdi, and 37.1% in Oju rely on piped or borehole water. Additionally, a significant proportion of households use streams or rivers as their drinking water sources, with 26.7% in Agatu, 19.5% in Kwande, and 23.8% in Oju. Furthermore, the utilization of rainwater as a drinking water source is notable, with 33.3% of households in Agatu, 29.7% in Buruku, 21.5% in Kwande, 12.7% in Logo, 4.9% in Makurdi, and 27.9% in Oju reporting its use. These findings suggest that, in designing community water interventions in Benue State, it is crucial to consider the diverse water sources and the varying degrees of reliance on each.

4.3 Awareness of Climate Change

The result of the level of awareness of climate change in study communities is summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Households Awareness of Climate Change in Benue State

Variable	Categories	Female		Male		Grand	
		Fre	%	Fre	%	total	%
Level of awareness of climate change	Extremely Aware	2	25.00%	6	75.00%	8	2
	Highly Aware	3	13.00%	20	87.00%	23	5.75

	Minimally Aware	89	53.90%	76	46.10%	165	41.25
	Moderately Aware	31	34.10%	60	65.90%	91	22.75
	Not aware at all	76	67.30%	37	32.70%	113	28.25
	Total					400	100
By which means have you been informed about climate change and its potential impact?	News media	45	32.40%	94	67.60%	139	26.03
	Extension services	2	28.60%	5	71.40%	7	1.31
	Workshops and training sessions	7	53.80%	6	46.20%	13	2.43
	Peer discussions	66	55.50%	53	44.50%	119	22.28
	Own observation, experience	65	54.20%	55	45.80%	120	22.47
	Others	88	64.70%	48	35.30%	136	25.47
	Total	201	50.30%	199	49.80%	534	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024. Note: Layer two is multiple Response

The findings presented in Table 3 illustrate a pronounced gender disparity in climate change awareness. Only 25% of females are extremely aware of climate change, compared to 75% of males. Conversely, 67.3% of females are not aware of climate change at all, in contrast to 32.7% of males. Additionally, 87% of males indicated a high level of awareness, compared to just 13% of females. Regarding means through which groups are informed about climate change, majority 71% and 67% of the male compared to females 28% and 32% are informed about climate change through extension services and mass media respectively. It can be observed from the data that, most of the respondents get to know about climate change through informal means such as peer discussion 22.3%, personal observation 22.5% and others.

4.4 Perception of Temperature and Rainfall changes in Benue state

Communities often hold valuable indigenous knowledge regarding environmental changes. The results of the community's perceptions on temperature and rainfall changes are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4: Perception of Temperature and Rainfall Changes in Benue State

			Agatu Freq	Buruku Freq	Kwande Freq	Logo Freq	Makurdi Freq	Oju Freq	Total	%
How would you access the temperature of this community within the last 10 years?	Decreased	2	3	22	1	23	22	73	18.25	
	I don't know	0	0	1	0	6	1	8	2	
	Increased	35	62	39	56	73	35	300	75	
	unchanged	0	0	17	0	2	0	19	4.75	
	Total							400	100	
How would you access the rainfall	Decreased	31	9	35	53	62	23	213	53.25	
	I don't know	0	0	1	0	4	1	6	1.5	
	Increased	6	55	22	3	35	33	154	38.5	

patterns of this community within the last 10 years?	Unchanged	0	1	21	1	3	1	27	6.75
	Total	37	65	79	57	104	58	400	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

The results presented in Table 4 indicate that a majority, 67.5% of respondents, agree that temperature has increased, compared to 25.8% who believe there has been a decrease. This significant proportion of respondents perceiving an increase in temperature suggests a common awareness of warming trends, aligning with broader global patterns of rising temperatures due to climate change (IPCC, 2023). In an interview, the executive director of an organisation focused on PWDs acknowledged the changing temperature patterns in Benue, stating:

"In the last 10 years, the heat has kept increasing while the rainy season has become shorter and the dry season longer. The heat is excruciating; temperatures often reach over 35-38 degrees, sometimes nearing 40. But with no electricity, we just manage to survive."

This response highlights the worsening climate conditions over the past decade, characterised by rising temperatures, shorter rainy seasons, and longer dry seasons.

On the other hand, a significant proportion of respondents (53.3%) reported a decrease in rainfall over the years, while 38.5% indicated an increase. These divergent perceptions underscore the complexity and localized nature of rainfall variability in the region. The qualitative data from interviews and focus group discussions further illuminate the perceived changes in rainfall patterns. A 50-year-old male farmer from Buruku Local Government Area (LGA) provided a detailed account of the fluctuations in rainfall over the years:

"The rate and pattern of rainfall over the years have not been constant, i.e., they vary. In the last year, we had an increased amount of rainfall that started late, while in some years we experience a low amount of rain which starts early but ceases for a long time before resuming."

Another religious male leader acknowledges the heat conditions in Benue state:

"Heatwaves have increased, and the sunshine is scorching. We used to refer to it as climate change, but now some people are using the term 'climate boiling.' It's no longer just global warming; it's now global boiling, and I agree with them because the intensity of the heatwaves is just too much."

A female woman leader from Agatu LGA also describes the inconsistency in rainfall within her community:

"The rainfall pattern has actually changed from what it used to be. Before now, farmers and everyone else could predict the rainy season—when it would start and stop, when to plant, when to harvest, and when not to plant. But now, the weather has everyone confused."

These testimonies underscore the variability in both the timing and quantity of rainfall. Over the past decade, there has been a notable shift in the onset of the rainy season, with some years experiencing a delayed start followed by increased rainfall, while others have seen an early onset followed by prolonged dry spells.

4.5 Perceive Climatic Phenomena Affecting Vulnerable Groups in Benue State

Table 5 elucidates the distribution of responses regarding the climatic phenomena impacting vulnerable groups in Benue state.

Table 5: Perceive Climatic Phenomena Affecting Vulnerable Groups in Benue State

Climatic Phenomena	Agatu %	Buruku %	Kwande %	Logo %	Makurdi %	Oju %	Total	%
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Less Rainfall	14.19	8.25	15.77	10.10	8.17	8.38	136	10.66
Increased Rainfall	2.70	2.43	3.73	1.44	2.29	1.20	30	2.35
Short period of rainy season	24.32	20.87	5.39	22.60	6.21	19.16	190	14.89
Flood	8.11	8.74	2.90	6.73	17.65	4.79	113	8.86
Heavy and long period of rain	1.35	2.91	8.71	1.92	5.56	7.78	63	4.94
Dry spell	22.97	25.24	29.88	23.56	14.71	24.55	293	22.96
Late onset of rainy season	19.59	28.64	22.41	23.08	24.18	23.35	303	23.75
Heatwaves	6.76	2.91	11.20	10.58	21.24	10.78	148	11.60
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100	1276	100.00

Source: Field Survey, 2024. Multiple Response

The data illustrated in Table 5 indicate that a considerable proportion of respondents, 23.8%, identified the delayed onset of the rainy season as the primary climatic phenomenon adversely affecting their activities particularly agricultural production. This concern is closely followed by 22.9% of respondents who reported experiencing prolonged dry spells. Additionally, 15% of the respondents highlighted the shortened duration of the rainy season as a key climatic challenge. Furthermore, 11.6% of respondents cited heatwaves as a detrimental climatic stressor affecting many households. A female religious leader from Makurdi vividly described the harsh heat conditions experienced in recent years:

“The heat we have experienced in recent years is very harsh and worse compared to what I remember in the past. This type of heat is the one that causes meningitis. We bathe more than six times a night before daybreak, and you know PHCN [Power Holding Company of Nigeria] does not provide electricity during the heat period. There is no sleep because of the heat.”

On the hand, the findings suggest that climatic variability, particularly the timing and duration of rainfall and the prevalence of high temperatures, critically affects vulnerable groups in Benue State as majority are farmers. During interviews, participants consistently mentioned the inconsistency in rainfall patterns over recent years. A female interviewee, a women leader from Buruku, revealed:

“The pattern of rain has not been stable in recent years. Some years ago, the rain started as early as March and continued, but in the past five years, the first rain has started around May and has not been sustained for the required duration for farm productivity.”

Similarly, a male participant from a focus group discussion in Makurdi concurred with this observation, noting: *“We usually have early rainfall that lasts for a long time, but for the past three to four years, this pattern has changed to late rainfall that only lasts for a few months. Last year, for example, I personally planted rice, and there was no rain at some point. When the rain started again, it was too much and flooded our rice farm.”*

Another interviewee, a traditional leader from Agatu LGA, acknowledged the inconsistency in rainfall patterns, particularly the late onset of rainfall and dry spells in the middle of the planting season. He stated:

“The rain starts late and ends early, with either too little rainfall or an excessive amount that can cause flooding, especially along the riverbank. For example, last year, most rice farmers who planted at a certain period did not have rain on their farms for about three months, resulting in poor yield due to drought.”

The responses suggest an observed shift in the seasonal rainfall patterns over recent years in Benue State, with rain starting later and not lasting as long as needed. The implication is that farmers might struggle with reduced yields due to the shorter rainy season, affecting crop growth and harvest times. This highlights the urgent need for adaptive strategies to mitigate the adverse impacts of climatic variability on agricultural productivity.

4.6 Potential Impact of Climate Variability on Livelihood of Vulnerable Groups in Benue State

The data summarized in Table 6 analyzes the perceived impacts of climate variability on livelihoods of vulnerable groups in Benue State.

Table 6: The Potential Impact of Climate Variability on Agriculture Production in Communities of Benue State

Reduced crop yield	Female	Male	Total
No	4.00%	4.06%	4.03%
Not sure	2.00%	0.51%	1.26%
Yes	94.00%	95.43%	94.71%
Incidence of insects/pest/diseases in crop			
No	3.98%	7.61%	5.78%
Not sure	2.99%	2.54%	2.76%
Yes	93.03%	89.85%	91.46%
Land degradation/ Decreasing soil fertility			
No	3.57%	8.08%	5.84%
Not sure	5.61%	7.07%	6.35%
Yes	90.82%	84.85%	87.82%
Post-harvest losses			
No	21.39%	20.51%	20.96%
Not sure	3.48%	5.13%	4.29%
Yes	75.12%	74.36%	74.75%
Reduce water availability			
No	20.90%	27.18%	23.99%
Not sure	4.48%	4.10%	4.29%
Yes	74.63%	68.72%	71.72%
Grand total			100.00%

The data presented in Table 6 shows 94% of females and 95% of males indicated that climate variability has directly resulted in reduced crop yields. A notable 93.03% of females and 89.85% of males concurred that climate variability has led to an increase in the incidence of insects, pests, and diseases affecting crops. Furthermore, 90.82% of females and 84.85% of males reported that climate variability has contributed to land degradation or decreased soil fertility. Additionally, 75.12% of females and 74.36% of males indicated that climate variability has led to post-harvest losses. Moreover, 74.63% of females and 68.72% of males stated that climate variability has reduced water availability for irrigation and domestic use. These findings suggest a gendered dimension to the perception of climate variability impacts. In nearly all categories, female respondents reported higher percentages, which may indicate that women perceive or experience these impacts more acutely than men. This could be attributed to gender roles in agriculture, household water management, and food security responsibilities.

Most participants in the interviews identified crop pests and diseases as the most prevalent climatic impacts affecting agricultural production. Notably, vegetable crops, which are predominantly cultivated by women, are the most affected. This places women farmers at a greater disadvantage, as they often rely on these crops for both household nutrition and income generation. The increased prevalence of pests and diseases threatens not only their agricultural productivity but also their economic independence and food security.

One female interviewee from Kwande LGA highlighted this issue, stating:

"Crop pests and diseases are the most significant risks we have experienced in recent years in our communities, especially affecting vegetables, which are mostly planted by women."

This challenge, according to the respondent, is further compounded by limited access to pest control resources and agricultural support services for women farmers, restricting their ability to respond effectively to these threats. Similarly, another woman farmer from Logo LGA noted the emergence of new invasive species, previously unknown to their communities, which are affecting crops such as groundnuts. She stated:

"Previously, groundnuts were not attacked by insect pests, but now we cannot store them for more than two months. The pests start affecting the crop while it is still on the farm. This was not known in our community before."

The statement emphasises that this issue was not known in the community before, suggesting that the introduction of these pests is a recent phenomenon. This lack of historical precedent implies that local farmers may lack the knowledge, experience, or resources to effectively combat these new pests, leaving their crops vulnerable. Since women play a critical role in small-scale farming, these changes not only impact their livelihoods but also exacerbate existing gender inequalities.

The data further reveal that 71.2% of respondents perceived a decline in the level of water availability in the communities. In an interview with an executive director of an NGO, she noted that:

"In rural communities, women are spending longer hours searching for water and even reducing their bathing time. I've worked in these areas and heard their complaints—they no longer have enough water for bathing or clean water for cooking. As a result, they're at risk of skin diseases and struggle to maintain hygiene during their periods because they're trying to conserve the little water they have."

This suggests a severe lack of access to clean water, which affects not only basic needs but also the well-being of these women. The need to spend longer hours searching for water adds to the already heavy workload of women in rural communities, reducing their time for other productive activities and contributing to gender inequality.

Another prominent issue that emerged during discussions with communities was the interplay between environmental changes and socio-economic factors, which are exacerbating conflicts and leading to forced migration and displacement. The respondents highlighted a direct link between environmental degradation, specifically the increasing dryness of the environment, and the intensification of conflicts between farmers and herders. A religious leader emphasized that the scarcity of resources both arable land for farming and grazing land for herders has become a central issue in these conflicts:

"The conflict in Benue now is because of the dryness of the environment and the struggle between farmers and herders. This is something everyone is familiar with—scarce resources are leading to clashes, with herders searching for grazing land and farmers looking for places to cultivate. This conflict has led to migration, with people moving from one place to another, and women ending up in IDP camps."

This statement suggests that the environmental stress caused by increasing aridity is exacerbating tensions over land use. The competition for dwindling resources is a key driver of conflict, with farmers vying for the same limited areas of productive land. As these conflicts escalate, they lead to significant displacement and migration, forcing individuals and families to leave their homes in search of safer and more viable living conditions.

4.8 Adaptive strategies Used by Households to Cope with Climate Variability in Benue state

The data summarized in Table 7 provides an in-depth analysis of the adaptive strategies employed by respondents to mitigate the impacts of climate variability in Benue State.

Table 7: Adaptation Options Households Use to Cope with the Impact of Climate Change

Adaptation Options	Female	Male	Total Freq.	Grand %
Drought resistant crops and early maturing varieties				
No	58.71%	50.75%	219	54.75%
Yes	41.29%	49.25%	181	45.25%
Use of agro-forestry (Tree plantation)				
No	58.21%	74.37%	265	66.25%
Yes	41.79%	25.63%	135	33.75%
Mulching				
No	32.34%	15.58%	96	24.00%
Yes	67.66%	84.42%	304	76.00%
Increase irrigation				
No	66.17%	53.27%	239	59.75%
Yes	33.83%	46.73%	161	40.25%
Intercropping				
No	22.89%	33.17%	112	28.00%
Yes	77.11%	66.83%	288	72.00%
Early and late planting				
No	19.90%	24.62%	89	22.25%
Yes	80.10%	75.38%	311	77.75%
Farming to non-farming				
No	55.22%	32.66%	176	44.00%
Yes	44.78%	67.34%	224	56.00%
Using traditional variety of crop				
No	17.91%	16.58%	69	17.25%
Yes	82.09%	83.42%	331	82.75%
Grand Total			400	100.00%

Sources: Field Survey, 2024

The data presented in the above table indicate that 41.29% of females, compared to 49.25% of males, have adopted drought-resistant crops and early maturing varieties. Despite the significant benefits of agroforestry, only 41.79% of females, compared to 25.63% of males, practice this method. A substantial 84.42% of males, compared to 67.66% of females, reported using mulching as a strategy to conserve soil moisture and reduce temperature fluctuations.

The adoption of irrigation practices was confirmed by 40.25% of respondents. This implies that the majority—67.17% of females compared to 53.2% of males—lack access to irrigation facilities, a crucial adaptation strategy that ensures a reliable water supply during periods of insufficient rainfall.

Intercropping, particularly the practice of planting legumes with cereals, was reported by 77.11% of females compared to 66.83% of males. A significant 80.10% of females, compared to 75.38% of males, indicated implementing measures such as early or late planting to align with changing climatic conditions.

Diversification into non-farming activities was reported by 44.78% of females compared to 67.34% of males, reflecting a strategic shift to reduce dependence on agriculture and mitigate the economic risks associated with climate variability. Finally, 82.09% of females and 83.42% of males reported utilizing traditional crop varieties, which are inherently more adaptable to climatic fluctuations.

5.0 Discussions of Results

The study findings reveal a significant gender gap in climate change awareness, with males demonstrating higher levels of awareness compared to females. This aligns with the respondents' educational profiles, as a substantial majority of females 75% compared to 57% of males have only attained lower levels of education. Supporting this, Ubong (2021) found that individuals with higher educational levels are more likely to be aware of climate change than those with limited education. This disparity suggests that females may be less informed about climate change issues, potentially limiting their participation in discussions and decision-making processes related to climate action. Prior research (Onah et al., 2022; Ume et al., 2021) has shown that women, particularly in rural and low-income communities, often bear the brunt of climate change impacts due to their roles in water collection, agriculture, and household energy management. The lower awareness among females may hinder their ability to adapt to and mitigate these impacts, thereby increasing their vulnerability.

The study further highlights that a significant portion of the population (92%) is either minimally aware or entirely unaware of climate change, underscoring the inadequacy of current efforts to educate the public in Benue State. A gender disparity in access to formal information channels was also observed, with men being more likely than women to receive climate change information through extension services and mass media. This suggests a need for targeted interventions to improve women's access to formal information sources.

Regarding climate change perceptions, the majority of respondents (75%) reported an increase in temperature, indicating a common awareness of warming trends. This observation aligns with global patterns of rising temperatures due to climate change (IPCC, 2023). The community's perception of increasing temperatures is supported by previous studies (David, 2024; Adeyemi, 2024), which conducted climate trend analyses in the study location. For instance, David (2024) reported that temperatures in Benue State have risen by 0.23°C per decade, while precipitation has decreased by 1.3 mm per decade over the past 30 years.

There were divergent responses regarding changes in rainfall patterns across study locations, with some respondents reporting an increase and others indicating a decreasing trend. Overall, a significant proportion (53.3%) perceived a decline in rainfall over the years. These variations underscore the localized and complex

nature of rainfall variability in the region. Scientific evidence supports this variability, with studies indicating that communities in the southern part of the state experience the most stable and abundant annual rainfall, whereas those in the north experience the least and most fluctuating rainfall (Idoko et al., 2023; David, 2024). Idoko et al. (2023) reported a significant downward trend in annual rainfall at northern stations, while the decline at southern stations was statistically insignificant. This variability has been attributed to a combination of climatic factors, including seasonal shifts and microclimatic conditions.

The study also identified delayed onset of the rainy season, reduced rainfall duration, and high temperatures as the primary climatic phenomena adversely affecting livelihoods, particularly agricultural production of the vulnerable groups in Benue state. According to respondents, irregular rainfall patterns pose significant challenges to agricultural planning and water management. The observed shift in rainfall patterns, particularly the delay in the onset of the rainy season and the occurrence of prolonged dry spells, has profound implications for agriculture in Benue State, where 52.5% of the population depends on crop farming as their primary source of income. Consequently, 94% of respondents reported that climate variability has directly led to reduced crop yields and the emergence of new pests and diseases. This finding is consistent with Doe (2021), who noted that planting and harvesting cycles are intricately linked to rainfall predictability, and deviations from expected patterns can disrupt these activities, leading to reduced yields and increased vulnerability to food insecurity.

The study further highlights significant gender disparities in the adoption of climate adaptation strategies. The findings indicate that men are more likely than women to adopt certain strategies, while women engage in specific practices influenced by differences in access to resources, decision-making roles, and traditional responsibilities. For instance, 49.25% of males compared to 41.29% of females have adopted drought-resistant crops and early-maturing varieties. This gap reflects gendered differences in access to agricultural inputs, extension services, and decision-making power within households. Furthermore, 67.17% of females compared to 53.2% of males reported lacking access to irrigation facilities, suggesting that women face more structural barriers, such as financial constraints. Socioeconomic data from the study indicate that men have better access to higher-paying jobs (30% of males compared to 10% of females), and a higher proportion of males earn more than their female counterparts. Additionally, when considering diversification into non-farming activities, men (67.34%) significantly outnumber women (44.78%). This suggests that men have greater opportunities for off-farm income and alternative livelihoods, whereas women are constrained by domestic responsibilities or cultural norms that limit their economic independence. These disparities suggest that women are more vulnerable to the impacts of climate change due to limited job opportunities and financial resources for adaptation. This aligns with the findings of Onah et al. (2023), which reported that female-headed farming households are more susceptible to climate change and variability than their male-headed counterparts, primarily due to greater exposure and lower adaptive capacity. Consequently, they experienced higher exposure to climate risks, reduced ability to recover from climate-related shocks, and increased dependency on external support. Given that over half of the respondents rely on crop farming, the community remains highly vulnerable to climate-related risks such as droughts and

extreme weather. Women, who often have lower incomes and fewer opportunities for formal employment, face greater economic hardships due to climate-induced agricultural losses.

Overall, these findings emphasize the need for targeted climate education programs, gender-inclusive adaptation strategies, and policy interventions that enhance women's access to information, resources, and economic opportunities to mitigate their vulnerability to climate change.

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